

Methylthymolblue complexon as corrosion inhibitors for aluminum in trichloroacetic acid

Piyush S. Desai^a and R. T. Vashi^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Arts, Science and Commerce College Kholwad, Kamrej Char Rrasta, Surat-394 185, Gujarat, India

E-mail : psdesai69@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Navyug Science College, Rander Road, Surat-395 009, Gujarat, India

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Abstract : The corrosion of aluminum in trichloroacetic acid (TCA) containing methylthymolblue complexon has been studied. In plain trichloroacetic acid, the corrosion rate increases with the acid concentration. At constant acid concentration, the inhibition efficiency (IE) of methylthymolblue complexon increases with the inhibitor concentration. At constant inhibitor concentration, the IE decreases with the increase of acid concentration. As temperature increases, percentage of inhibition decreases. Plot of $\log (\theta/1 - \theta)$ versus $\log C$ results in a straight line, suggesting that the inhibitors cover both the anodic and cathodic regions through general adsorption following Langmuir isotherm. The curves show very little anodic but significant cathodic polarization.

Keywords : Corrosion, aluminum, trichloroacetic acid, methylthymolblue complexon.

Introduction

Aluminum is known to exhibit passive behaviour in aqueous solutions. The corrosion of the metal has been reported to depend on processes associated with the passivating surface oxide film such as metal ion transfer to the metal/oxide interface, metal ion and oxygen ion transfer to the oxide/solution interface, ion migration in the oxide film, and electron transfer from the metal to acceptor species in solution¹. Different kinds of dyes are known viz. heterocyclic dyes, xanthene dyes, anthraquinone dyes and azo dyes. In fact, about half of the dyes in industrial use today are azo dyes, which are mostly prepared from diazonium salts². Talati studied the xanthenes and azo dyes as corrosion inhibitors for aluminum in TCA³. Ebenso studied (Part Two of the series) methyl red (MR) and halide ions are being investigated as inhibitors for the corrosion of aluminum in H₂SO₄ solutions both individually and in conjunction⁴. The present article reports the inhibitive action of methylthymolblue complexon on the corrosion of aluminum in TCA solutions using gravimetric as well as polarization method.

Results and discussion

The results are presented in Tables 1 to 3 and Figs.

1 to 3. To assess their protective value, methylthymolblue complexon was added to solutions of trichloroacetic acid. The pH of plain 0.01 M TCA was found to be 2.02 while the inhibited acid (0.01 M TCA + 1 mM inhibitors) was observed 2.05 (methylthymolblue complexon), i.e. the inhibitors have no effect on the pH of the acid.

Effect of acid concentration : The effect of acid concentration on the inhibitive efficiency of the methylthymolblue complexon is shown in Table 1. The IE decreases with the increase in acid concentration.

Effect of inhibitor concentration : At constant acid concentration, the IE of the methylthymolblue complexon increases with the inhibitor concentration, e.g. in 0.10 M TCA the IE was found to be 87.10, 94.49, 95.61 and 96.60% with respect to 1, 2, 3 and 4 mM inhibitor concentration respectively (Table 1).

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature on the corrosion of aluminum is shown in Table 2. It shows that the increase in corrosion rate may be due to thermal activated kinetic⁵. The IE for methylthymolblue complexon was decreased (85.16, 83.14 and 80.58% at 313, 323 and 333 K respectively at 4 mM inhibitor

Table 1. Effect of acid concentration on corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm) and inhibition efficiency (%) of aluminum containing different dyes inhibitors

Effective area of specimen : 0.2414 sq. dm, immersion period : 24 h, temp. : 301 ± 1 K

Inhibitor	Inhibitor concentration (mM)	Acid concentration					
		0.01 M		0.05 M		0.10 M	
		Corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm)	IE (%)	Corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm)	IE (%)	Corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm)	IE (%)
Blank	-	118.88	-	1189.3	-	2452.09	-
Methyl-thymolblue complexon	1	0.01	99.99	33.95	97.09	316.32	87.10
	2	0.01	99.99	26.51	97.77	135.11	94.49
	3	0.01	99.99	15.46	98.70	107.65	95.61
	4	0.01	99.99	9.51	99.20	83.37	96.60

concentration) with raising the temperature.

Mean E_a value were calculated by using eq. (2) for aluminum in 0.05 M TCA is 33.83 kJ mol⁻¹ while in acid containing inhibitors, the mean E_a values are found to be higher than that of uninhibited system (Table 2). The higher values of mean E_a indicate physical adsorption of the inhibitors on metal surface⁶, which leads to an increase in the energy barrier for the corrosion process⁷. The values of E_a calculated from the slope of Arrhenius plot (Fig. 1) and using eq. (2) are almost similar.

From Table 2 it is evident that in all the cases the values of Q_{ads} are negative, the values ranging from -26.85 kJ mol⁻¹ to -12.74 kJ mol⁻¹. The negative values show that the adsorption, and hence the inhibition efficiency, decreases with a rise in temperature⁸.

The mean ΔG_a^0 values are negative almost in all

Fig. 1. Arrhenius plots for corrosion of aluminum in 0.05 M trichloroacetic acid in absence and presence of 4 mM inhibitor concentration : (★) blank, (■) methylthymolblue complexon.**Table 2.** Effect of temperature on corrosion loss (CL), inhibitive efficiency (%), energy of activation (E_a), heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}) and free energy of adsorption for aluminum in 0.05 M TCA contain inhibitorsImmersion period : 2 h, effective specimen area : 0.2414 dm²

System	Temp. (K)						Mean E_a from eq. (2) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	E_a from Arrhenius plot (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Q_{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)		Mean value (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	313		323		333				313-	323-	(ΔG_a^0)	(ΔH_a^0)	(ΔS_a^0)
	CL (mg/dm ²)	IE (%)	CL (mg/dm ²)	IE (%)	CL (mg/dm ²)	IE (%)			323 K	333 K			
A	194.70	-	310.68	-	426.68	-	33.83	32.61	-	-	-	-	-
B	40.69	79.10	82.85	73.33	128.3	69.93	49.41	47.69	-26.85	-14.99	-32.15	36.42	0.2119
C	34.31	82.39	62.48	79.89	103.21	75.81	47.65	45.77	-13.69	-21.21	-30.76	42.21	0.2241
D	31.05	84.05	57.76	81.41	95.45	77.63	48.35	46.67	-15.56	-20.8	-30.28	42.25	0.2247
E	28.90	85.16	52.38	83.14	82.85	80.58	45.5	43.77	-12.74	-15.45	-29.85	38.31	0.2111

A = Trichloroacetic acid, B = trichloroacetic acid + 1 mM methylthymolblue complexon, C = trichloroacetic acid + 2 mM methylthymolblue complexon, D = trichloroacetic acid + 3 mM methylthymolblue complexon, E = trichloroacetic acid + 4 mM methylthymolblue complexon.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log (\theta / 1-\theta)$ versus $\log C$ for methylthymolblue complexon in 0.01 M trichloroacetic acid concentration.

cases and lie in the range of -32.85 to -29.85 kJ mol^{-1} (methylthymolblue complexon). The negative mean value of ΔG_{ads}^0 suggest that the inhibitor molecules are strongly adsorbed on the metal surface; the values also indicate a spontaneous adsorption of the inhibitor molecules and usually characterize their strong interactions with the metal surface. This is usually characteristic of strong interactions with the metal surface. It is found that the ΔG_a^0 values are more positive than -40 kJ mol^{-1} indicating that inhibitors are physically adsorbed on the metal surface^{9,10}.

The enthalpy changes (ΔH_a^0) are positive indicating the endothermic nature of the reaction¹¹ suggesting that higher temperature favours the corrosion process. The entropy (ΔS_a^0) values are positive confirming that the corrosion process is entropically favourable¹².

Open circuit potential : A specimen of aluminum when immersed in 0.01 M TCA developed a steady state potential of -689 mV vs SCE. In the presence of 1 mM methylthymolblue complexon the corrosion potentials was decreased (-698) than the blank.

Polarization behaviour : The polarization behaviour of aluminum in 0.01 M TCA at 1 mM inhibitor concentration under galvanostatic conditions at different current densities in presence and absence of inhibitors is shown in Fig. 3. The values of corrosion current densities in the presence and absence of inhibitor were obtained from the graph while percentage efficiency was calculated using the relation :

$$IE(\%) = [i_{\text{corr}}(U) - i_{\text{corr}}(i)/i_{\text{corr}}(U)] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The curves show both anodic and cathodic polarization. Thus the open circuit potentials and galvanostatic polarization data suggest that the inhibitors function through general adsorption on cathodic as well as anodic sites

Fig. 3. Polarisation curves for corrosion of aluminum in 0.01 M trichloroacetic acid containing 1 mM dyes as inhibitor : (★) blank, (■) methylthymolblue complexon.

on the metal surface.

Mechanism :

Generally, aluminum dissolves in acid solutions due to hydrogen evolution type of attack. The reaction-taking place at the micro electrodes of the corrosion cell being represented as under,

followed by the reaction

In the case of dissolution of aluminum in TCA the reaction in the initial stages appear to be¹³

Methylthymolblue complexon is a class of sulphophthalein dyes. This dyestuff which forms complexes with specific metal cations can serve as indicator¹⁴. According to the work of Talati *et al.*¹⁵ corrosivity may be explained in the following manner if the metal-colorants complex is more stable at lower pH values; is insoluble and formed *in situ* on the metal surface, the extent of corrosion decreases. Usually, corrosion inhibitors containing atoms of nitrogen, sulphur or oxygen have electron donating ability and their action is attributed to the adsorption of the inhibitor molecules on the metal surface through an unshared pair of electrons belonging to the functional atom¹⁶.

Experimental

Rectangular specimens of size $5.0 \times 2.0 \times 0.18$ cm having an area of 0.2414 sq. dm of 2S grade aluminum with small hole of about 5 mm diameter near the upper edge, were used for the determination of the corrosion

Table 3. Polarisation data and inhibition efficiency of organic dyes for aluminum in 0.01 M trichloroacetic acid

Surface area of specimen : 0.02585 sq. dm, inhibitor concentration : 1 mM

System	E_{corr} (mV)	Corrosion current density from intersection of anodic and cathodic Tafel ines I_{corr} (A/cm ²)	Tafel slope (mV/decade)			Inhibition efficiency (%)	
			Cathodic - β_c	Anodic + β_a	B (mV)	Polarisation (%)	Weight loss (%)
Blank	-755	0.082	6250	231	97	-	-
methylthymolblue complexon	-793	0.010	1489	114	46	87.80	99.99

 β_a = Anodic Tafel constant, β_c = cathodic Tafel constant.

rate. The specimens were polished according to the method described earlier^{17,18}. The specimens were degreased by immersion in A.R. grade acetone and dried in warm air using air dryer and preserved in dessicator till use. The test specimens were immersed in 0.01, 0.05 and 0.10 M TCA solution with and without inhibitors. Methylthymolblue complexon was used as inhibitors in 1, 2, 3 and 4 mM concentration. One specimen only was suspended by a glass hook, in each beaker containing 230 ml of the test solution and was open to the air at room temperature for 24 h. After the tests, the specimens were cleaned with chromic-phosphate mixture solution¹⁹. Triplicate experiments were performed in each case and the mean value of the weight loss data we presented in mg/sq. dm.

To study the effect of temperature on corrosion rate, the specimen were immersed in 230 ml in 0.05 M trichloroacetic acid, with 1, 2, 3 and 4 mM for methylthymolblue complexon inhibitor concentration at solution temperatures of 313, 323 and 333 K for a period of 2 h. For the purpose of temperature effect study, thermostat assembly with accuracy of ± 0.5 °C was used. Wesley²⁰ and ASTM²¹ pointed out that thermostatic control within ± 1 °C usually is considered satisfactory. From the data IE, energy of activation (E_a), heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}), free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}^0), were calculated and shown in Table 2.

Aluminum specimen having an area of 0.0675 dm² was immersed in 0.01 M TCA with and without 1 mM inhibitor concentration and the potential was recorded against the saturated calomel electrode every 2 min, till a constant potential was attained.

For polarization study, metal specimens of rectangular design having an area of 0.02585 dm² were exposed to corrosive solutions. Aluminum metal was used as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl was used as refer-

ence electrode and auxiliary platinum electrode was placed in a 100 ml corrosive media through which external current was supplied automatically from computerized polarization instrument. The change in potential was measured by potentiostat/galvanostat (Autolab Model-273). Galvanostatic polarization has been taken with and without inhibitors in 0.01 M trichloroacetic acid.

Inhibition efficiency (IE) in percentage has been calculated as follows :

$$IE = [(W_u - W_i)/W_u] \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where W_u is the weight loss of the metal in uninhibited acid and W_i is the weight loss of a metal in inhibited acid.

Energy of activation (E_a) has been calculated from the slopes of $\log p$ versus $1/T$ (p = corrosion rate, T = absolute temperature) and also with the help of Arrhenius equation²².

$$\log p_2/p_1 = E_a/2.303 R[(1/T_1) - (1/T_2)] \quad (7)$$

where p_1 and p_2 are the corrosion rate at temperature T_1 and T_2 respectively.

The values of heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}) were calculated by the following equation²²

$$Q_{ads} = 2.303 R [\log (\theta_2/1 - \theta_2) - \log (\theta_1/1 - \theta_1)] \times [T_1 \cdot T_2 / T_2 - T_1] \quad (8)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 [$\theta = (W_u - W_i)/W_i$] are the fraction of the metal surface covered by the inhibitors at temperature T_1 and T_2 , respectively.

The values of the free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}^0) were calculated with slope of the following equation²³

$$\log C = \log (\theta/1 - \theta) - \log B \quad (9)$$

where $\log B = -1.74 - (\Delta G_{ads}^0/2.303 RT)$ and C is the

inhibitor concentration.

The enthalpy of adsorption (ΔH_{ads}^0) and entropy of adsorption (ΔS_{ads}^0) were calculated using the following eqs. (10) and (11).

$$\Delta H_{\text{ads}}^0 = E_a - RT \quad (10)$$

$$T\Delta S_{\text{ads}}^0 = \Delta H_{\text{ads}}^0 - \Delta G_{\text{ads}}^0 \quad (11)$$

Conclusions :

The corrosion rate of aluminum metal in TCA was increase with the acid concentration.

- (i) At constant acid concentration, the IE of methylthymolblue complexon increased with increasing inhibitor concentration.
- (ii) As the temperature increases corrosion rate increases in plain acid.
- (iii) The E_a values for inhibited system are higher than the uninhibited system. The higher values of mean E_a indicate physical adsorption of the inhibitors on metal surface.
- (iv) The mean free energy of adsorption, ΔG_{ads}^0 negative, suggesting that the inhibitor molecules be strongly adsorbed on the metal surface.
- (v) $\log(\theta/1 - \theta)$ vs $\log C$ (inhibitor concentration) shows straight line, which indicates that the inhibition action appears to be the chemisorptions and inhibitors cover both anodic and cathodic region through general adsorption following Langmuir isotherm (Fig. 2).
- (vi) At all inhibitor concentration in 0.01 M acid concentration methylthymolblue complexon shows better IE (99.99%).

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